

Tautomeric Products of Condensation of Aromatic Aldehydes with Pyrazolone

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Three products have been obtained by the condensation of aromatic aldehydes under different conditions with a 5-pyrazolone containing a reactive methylene group. The two bis-pyrazolone compounds are keto-enol tautomeric forms; one form shows carbonyl group absorption at 5.75μ in I.R. and the other form shows no peak between 5μ and 6μ . *p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde produces the same product under different conditions.

Several condensation reactions take place at the active methylene group of 5-pyrazolone. Orthoformic ester, formamide, or chloroform-alkali condenses with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone to furnish 4,4'-methenyl-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) (Perroncito, Attix Congr. Internaz. Chem., 1938, III, 267-276). Aromatic aldehydes react with pyrazolones containing active methylene group, e.g., the formation of tautomeric products by condensation with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (Porai and Malikova, *Izvest. Akad. Nauk, S. S. S. R., Otdel Khim. Nauk*, 1948, 519). It appears from available literature that the products of reaction of aromatic aldehydes with pyrazolone under different conditions has not been fully studied. In the present investigation, the reaction of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes in acidic, alkaline, and neutral media has been studied. The formation of mono-heterocyclic or bis-heterocyclic products is found to be governed by the nature of the medium.

Benzaldehyde reacts with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone in acetic acid solution to afford two products—red crystals of 4-benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone, m.p. 107° and pale yellow crystals of benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone), m.p. $161-63^\circ$. Reaction of benzaldehyde with parent pyrazolone in ethanolic medium in presence of piperidine produces only one product, a colorless crystalline compound, m.p. $203-205^\circ$. This last product is converted to the above pale yellow crystals, m.p. $161-63^\circ$, when its ethanolic solution is treated with dilute sulphuric acid or the solid is treated with glacial acetic acid. Refluxing of the product (m.p. $161-63^\circ$) with piperidine in ethanolic medium regenerates the product, m.p. $203-205^\circ$. Refluxing with piperidine in the same medium also converts the red crystalline product, m.p. 107° , to the colorless product, m.p. $203-205^\circ$.

by the above treatment. Ethanolic solution of the hydrochloride is acidic to litmus and develops a violet colour with ferric chloride solution. Its aqueous extract gave no turbidity with silver nitrate solution, but it gave silver chloride on refluxing with ethanolic silver nitrate solution. It is soluble in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.3. $C_{27}H_{26}O_2N_4Cl_2$ requires C, 63.65; H, 5.1%).

Conversions of Benzylidenemonopyrazolone and the Bis-pyrazolone

Benzylidenemonopyrazolone, m.p. 107° , was dissolved in rectified spirit; a few drops of piperidine were added and the mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hour. White crystalline solid, m.p. $203-205^\circ$, separated from the hot solution. Mixed m.p. of the above product with benzylidene-bis-diol was not depressed.

The bis-diol was dissolved in a minimum volume of glacial acetic acid at room temperature and left overnight. Water was added next day till turbidity appeared. A pale yellow crystalline solid was collected after 1 hour, m.p. $161-63^\circ$.

The conversion of the enol to carbonyl could also be carried out in the following manner. To the bis-diol, dissolved in 10% aqueous NaOH at room temperature, solid ammonium chloride was added and the mixture was warmed when a precipitate came down. It was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. $161-63^\circ$. Refluxing with either ammonia or pyridine in ethanolic solution did not convert the carbonyl compound to the enolic tautomer.

Methoxy Derivative of Diol

To benzylidene-4,4'-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) (1 g.), dissolved in aqueous NaOH (0.2 g. in 10 c.c.), dimethyl sulphate (0.25 g.) was added. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hours, extracted with ether, and the extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether was removed and the residue was crystallised from acetone as granular, colorless crystals, m.p. 179° .

The above product gave no coloration with ferric chloride. It is insoluble in aqueous alkali. (Found: C, 75.04; H, 5.7. $C_{29}H_{28}O_2N_4$ requires C, 75.01; H, 6.03%).